

Intention between International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) and Islamic Religion Proposing a conceptual framework for intention to be included in IFRS

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Dr. Khaled Jamal Jaarat ⁽²⁾Eman Abu Amr
Middle East University Jordan

Abstract

The study aimed to identify rules of intention in Islamic religion, Develop a conceptual framework of intention consider that most of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) without any conceptualization, also, identify the places where the intention exists in IFRSs, and finally identify the accepted and unaccepted accounting practices in which intention plays an important role.

Researchers used the qualitative method, where they used actual financial statements of the Jordanian public shareholding companies included in the sample during the period 2006 - 2015, in addition, they used structured interviews.

The study concluded to the possibility of setting a conceptual framework to intention in IFRSs derived from Islamic religion and incorporating it into the qualitative characteristics within the fundamental characteristic: representational faithfulness.

The researchers recommended the necessity of adopting the proposed conceptual framework of intention by International Accounting Standards Board(IASB), to improve the documentation process for the purposes of recognition of elements in financial statements, and work more to increase the interest of audit firms in enhancing the professional skepticism of their employees, in addition to the need of establishing wide time series financial databases in companies to facilitate the control of their intentions and their conformity with the accounting practices carried out by these companies.

Keywords: *Intention, international financial reporting standards, Islamic religion*

Introduction

International Financial Reporting Standards(IFRS) considered to be the suitable method to make accounting practices characterized by reliability, that characteristic – reliability- improve the acceptance, representational faithfulness of accounting figures, that because it was prepared according to set of standards, easily can be referred to in order to be assured that the accounting information resulted from processing objective and real data, also, related judgments and alternative treatments and intended adoption of it can be identified through disclosures, so as financial statements could include high-quality information that assists users in rationalizing their decisions.

Most of IFRS include the concept of Intention without giving this concept a clear definition, or identifying details to how intention can be judged, that because difficulty of measuring or controlling it, as a result of changeable features, intangible existence, qualitative characteristics, in spite of mention it as a basic and fundamental requirement to apply specific IFRS in some accounting practices(IASB, 2016).

Importance of intentions considered to be very high, since to its role in identifying many accounting practices, but related studies that investigate in relationship between intention and actions or practices are very rare, like Suaidan(2007) that summarized the rules of intention by fourteen rules will be discussed later, also Faraj(2012) that aimed to discussed the impact of using expert systems in accounting estimation to provisions especially allowance for doubtful depts., beside Schipper(2012) that discussed how business model that adopted by management reflects the non declared intention behind its practices, the latter study indicates the recurring of using intention concepts in IFRS, finally, discussed the classification of financial instruments according to intention of entity and its effect on financial statements.

Researchers will try this study to set a conceptual framework for intention in IFRS derived from Islamic religion, that considered as the lonely setter of detailed explanation and comprehensive to intention concept.

Problem of the study and its question

Despite the fact that intention concept widely used in IFRS, but there is no declared and specific definition or framework to it, also, sometimes intention considered to be the core in formulating many accounting practices, in reality, there are no sufficient disclosures to intentions behind accounting practices, especially at initial recognition of items that intention very important in classifying then measuring it, led to misleading

information used by decision makers resulted in mistakenly decisions, in spite of some IFRS declared clearly the requirement of disclosing intention and related matters, but there is no commitment from preparers to do that.

Depending on aforementioned, the problem of the study can be questioned by the following main question:” Is it possible to set a conceptual framework to intention in IFRS derived from Islamic religion and include it within accompanied disclosures of financial statements?”

Sub-questions the main question can be as follow:

- 1- Is there a relationship between intention and recognition, measurement, and classification of items included in financial statements?
- 2- Does IFRS include disclosures relate to documentation and declaration of intention?
- 3- Does Islamic religion include a conceptual framework to intention can, that can be benefited from it to set and amend IFRS?

Importance of the study and its Objectives

This study gained its importance from considering at as a serious try to set a conceptual framework to intention clarify intention mentioned in IFRS, and determine the missed connection point between the hidden intention of related parties that preparing financial statements, and its reflections in these statements, the study aims to s=achieve the following goals:

- 1- Introducing intention and its framework in the Islamic religion.
- 2- Setting a conceptual framework to intention in IFRS, and including it in disclosures accompanied by the financial statements.
- 3- Identifying places in IFRS that intention considered to be the main determinant in its recognition.
- 4- Identifying accepted accounting practices that intention plays an important role in it.

Limitations and Determinants

Limitations are two types: the first is time limitations since the study conducted on financial statements during the period 2006 to 2015, the second is place limitations, the study conducted in on the Jordanian public shareholding companies in Amman stock exchange.

Determinants are: the scarcity of related previous studies on local, regional, and international levels, also, there are no standards or controls to reveal what is hidden inside people, besides the difficulty of quantitative measurement of intention that lead to difficulties in forecasting the in-actions of people.

Methodology of the study and its tool

Researchers adopted the qualitative analytical method, since the study is exploratory one, they analyze actual data presented in financial statements of the corporations included in the sample during the period between 2006 and 2015, also several interviews with the specialists to identify intention, bad and good, that proceed directly recognition, measurement, and disclosure in financial statements, researchers collected data from two sources: the first is **theoretical** source through books, journals and researches that relate to the study, whether from accounting or Islamic point view, researchers benefit from these studies in identifying the concepts of the study, besides its problem and assumptions, the second is practical source through studying and analyzing financial statements of the corporations included in the sample during 2006 to 2015, besides interviews conducted with related persons, **tool** of the study is financial statements and interviews.

Intention in Islamic religion

Intention mentioned in main sources of Islamic religion directly, or indirectly through synonyms that compact with intention in meaning, in Quran, Sunna of prophet Mohammed – peace be upon him- through his Hadiths, or Islamic jurisprudence in explaining intention concept, its precedence, and its great status in Islam, as follow:

- A. **In Quran:** mentioned as purity and sincerity , Allah the highest says: "And they were commanded not, but that they worship Allah, and worship none but Him Alone(abstaining from ascribing partners to Him)and perform As-Salat(Iqamat-as-Salat)and give Zakat, and that the right religion"(Surat Al-Bayyinah, 5), also, mentioned as seeking in saying of Allah the highest: "O, Prophet! Why do you forbid(for yourself) that which Allah has allowed to you, seeking to please your wives? And Allah is Oft-Forgiving, Most Merciful"(Surat At-Tahrim, 1), also mentioned as desire in saying of Allah the highest:" and whoever desires the hereafter and strives for it, with the necessary effort due for it(i.e. does righteous deeds of Allah's Obedience) while he is a believer (in the Oneness of Allah-Islamic Monotheism)-then such are the ones whose striving shall be appreciated, thanked and rewarded by Allah" "(Surat Al-Isra', 19).
- B. **In Sunna:** Hadith of Umar Ibn Al-Khattab said: I heard Allah's Messenger- peace be upon him- saying, "The reward of deeds depends upon the intentions and every person will receive the rewards according to what he has intended. So, whoever emigrates for the sake of Allah and His Messenger, his emigration will be (counted as being) for Allah and His Messenger, and whoever emigrates for worldly benefits or for a woman to marry, his emigration will be (counted as being) for what he emigrated for"(Bukhari, 1/6). Also, Abu Hurairah narrated that the Messenger of Allah -peace be upon him- said: "The oath is based upon what will make your companion believe you." "(Moslem, 1653/3).
- C. Some of the **Islamic jurists** mentioned that every action and practice must accompany with intention, for example Al-Baghdadi(1996) said: "those who desire to have the best action, his intention must be good, because Allah the highest hires the people if they improve their intentions", Ibn Al-Mobarak also said: "A small employer improves his intention, and a big employer minimizes his intention", Al-Fadail Ibn Ayyad said:"Allah the highest want your intention and well".

Definition of Intention in Islam

Intention (Niyyah) can be defined as a concept : determination to do something, in the Islamic religion, intention can be defined as the purpose of worship in actions to come closer to Allah, or purpose of doing something accompanied by action.

Place of Intention: As intention is a hidden practice, so its place is at heart, for the saying of the Messenger of Allah -peace be upon him- as narrated by Ibn 'Abbas said:" Verily Allah has pardoned [or been lenient with] for me my Ummah [community of Muslim believers]: their mistakes, their forgetfulness, and that which they have been forced to do under duress" (Bukhari,6/5269), some said that the place of intention in brain, others in both: heart and brain.

Timing of Intention: Jurists (Alfukahas) said that the timing of intention is before actions and sayings took place, Ahmad Ibn Hanbal said:" I like for every action as pray (Salat), fast(Siyam), ...etc, to have pre-intention for each(Hanbali, 2004), Soyati said that principally the timing of intention is in the initially of worship.

Places of intention in accounting practices, and what match it in Islam

1.Accounting errors and fraud: a)Error: may be defined according to International Standard on Auditing ISA 240 as unintentional misstatement in financial statements, including the omission of an amount or a disclosure, such as the following(IFAC, 2017):

- A mistake in gathering or processing data from which financial statements are prepared.
- An incorrect accounting estimate is arising from oversight or misinterpretation of facts.

- A mistake in the application of accounting principles relating to measurement, recognition, classification, presentation or disclosure.

In general, practices of preparers of financial statements rarely do not include errors because full integrity and rationality one of characteristics of his Allah the highest, these errors are unintentional practices, that is mean there is no pre-intention to do such practices, on the contrary of fraud, so these errors considered to be usual and recurring events in accounting, reflected in insufficient disclosures to those fundamental events took place in the accounting period that affected decisions of users of financial statements. As a result, errors would not consider being influenced by pre-intention to do it.

Fraud: fraud defined according to International Standard on Audit (IAS) 240, article 1a/a: "An intention act by one or more individuals among management, those charged with governance, employees, or third parties involving the use of deception to obtain an unjust or illegal advantage"(IFAC, 2016). Fraud include two types: the first relates to management fraud through manipulation in accounts for the purposes of overstating profit, and smoothing financial performance, resulted in deceiving users of financial statements, second relates to employees fraud that aims to cover thefts of assets, fraud had several forms such as manipulation, modifying of documents and accounting books, assets theft, intentional avoidance of applying accounting policies.

According to what mentioned, researchers conclude that fraud and manipulation both express intention of management to do bad actions, so as to achieve hidden interests and present misstated financial statements to users, beside personal objectives to be achieved by management to overstating the result of business, for the purposes of benefiting from the financial incentives and capital gains as a result of increasing prices of entity shares that may be acquired by them, because of that, the intention behind these practices preceded recognition of manipulated or cancelled items.

2. Accounting alternatives: intention incorporates accounting behaviors in the form of intimation which stimulates the person who prepared the financial statements for the selection of the most appropriate alternative that achieves the highest return and the best benefit, indicating clearly to the degree of freedom and flexibility enjoyed by IFRSs in the presence of multiple alternatives for accounting practices. Different accounting measurement bases, accounting policies, methods of accounting estimates, etc., all of them based on the intent behind used one alternative from other. Thus, the intention is clearly shown in the financial statements through the study of quantitative results in the statement of financial position depending on the desired goal of choosing the most appropriate alternative.

An entity before recognizes the item which has different methods to measure and influenced by one selection of an accounting policy or certain accounting estimate; should disclose of reasons from this choice. Examples of some policies and estimates that are used to treat the same events in the same economic entities:

1. Methods of Inventory Pricing according to IAS 2 : Inventories.
2. Estimate Useful life of non-current assets and the residual values for the purposes of calculating the annual depreciation, according to IAS 16 : property, plant, and equipment'.
3. Estimate the fair value according to IFRS 13: Fair value measurement.
4. Estimate of cash flows and the discount rate for the purposes of assessing value in use, in according to IAS 36: impairment of assets
5. Estimate doubtful debts and bad debts.
6. Estimate the technical obsolescence in non-current assets to IAS 36: impairment of assets .
7. estimate the reserve of natural resources for the purpose of calculating the depletion fiscal year as mentioned in standard IFRS 6 : Exploration for and evaluation of mineral resources.

3- Going concern hypothesis: When preparing financial statements, management must assess the ability of the entity to continue lasting forever in the foreseeable future, and make sure there is no intention to liquidate or reduce the size of their operations. This is achieved by following analytical and quantitative methods depending on financial ratios to judge entity failure or continuity of it, this fact must be disclosed through the reporting report and examined by external auditor, as stated in conceptual framework of financial statements of IASB, and IAS 1: presentation of financial statements, also, IAS 10 considers the absence of continuity is a modified event after reporting period till authorization date.

4- Offsetting

According to IAS 12: income taxes, it is permitted to offset current tax assets against current tax liabilities in the statement of financial position only if the entity has the legal right and intention at the same time to repay this obligation that subjected by tax authorities. We note that the intention of reimbursement has been reported in IAS 12 which is related to the income tax, but without addressing its details.

5- Business combination

Sometimes the entities acquire other entities, not for the purposes of achieving profits, but to get rid of its competitors, so, acquirer intends not to use non-financial assets obtained activity, or condone to use it according to the highest and best use, to achieve that goal, acquirer spends many expenses in the acquiree on research and studies without obtaining any benefits, but just to weaken its financial position and dispose it legally, it does not disclose this intention in the financial statements (Ernest & young, 2016).

6- Reclassification of financial assets

The reclassification of financial assets relates accompanied by the intention from the acquisition of these assets at the initial recognition of it.

IFRSs permitted the reclassification of financial assets if there was a change in the intention of the entity beyond the acquisition of these assets, or if the entity has not been able to keep these assets for a longer period of time. Sometimes the real intentions behind the reclassification are ambiguous. For example, an entity choosing a particular time to convert the investments from held for trading -management's intends to convert it into cash within a year or the operating cycle, whichever is longer- to the available for sale, or vice versa, or from HFT to the held-to-maturity or vice versa, and there are no controls on these intentions, just the faithful and objectivity(Jaarat, 2017).

The most prominent example of exploiting the intention of re-classifications of financial assets what occurred during the global financial crisis in 2008 and which led to the recognition of unrealized profits in the statement of profit and loss and other comprehensive income.

7- Treasury shares

Treasury shares are Ownership instruments re-purchased by the issuer. The cost of re-purchased deducted from the owner's equity, gains and losses relating to purchased or sold such shares are recognized are recognized directly in the owner equity but not in profit or loss or other comprehensive income, the reason, why issuer does that, depends on the intention and could be not one of the followings:

- Reduce the company capital.
- Distribution of profits in the form of free shares by using treasury shares.
- To enrich shareholders equity by increasing dividend payments as a result of the distribution of profits realized on fewer shares outstanding.
- To increase the demand for the company's shares at lower prices for reasons unrelated to the performance of the company.
- Reducing the number of free shares traded and thus causing higher prices to limit the control of some shareholders.
- It is possible to be hidden reasons behind the intention of reducing the assets of the entity to increase its commitments and which it reflects in decline in equity by the same amount, so affects the tax base of the company.

8- Earnings management

Earning management defined by (Mulford & Coniskey, 2002) as a manipulation useful in accounting results in order to find a different perception of the real performance of the company".

And usually these practices take an essential two dimensions:

- a. Increase profits in the current period compared to the prior periods and future periods.
- b. Reduced profit in the current period compared to the previous periods or future periods.

Researchers believe that earnings management is one of the accounting practices that fall under the concept of creative accounting, which has two faces of the same coin, it is not easy to differentiate between the truth and falsity. On the one hand reflects the reliability of a certain truth in the financial statements, on the other hand, it is used as a method of fraud and manipulation to deceive the users of these statements. The rule here is the ethical, moral and technical dimensions of the reality behind the intention of preparers of financial statements from applying such practices hidden intentions not declared to the users of these statements.

Earnings management is one of the most modern and controversial practices in the science of accounting, which is taken by the administration as a deliberate practices through which the financial statements are produced to the distortion in the financial performance of the business, leading to influence positively or negatively on the net profit, and thus affect the decisions of users of financial statements.

Timing of the intention according to IFRSs derived from Islamic religion

Recognition of an item in the statement of financial position needs to be some reason to express what is going on in the mind of the management for the purpose of measurement and classification. This reason comes from the intention of management before the event takes place and guided preparers voluntarily to achieve a certain goal.

Referring to Islamic religion, all Jurists (Alfukahas) allocate intentions before initial step of doing actions not after it, according to Hadith of Umar Ibn Al-Khattab said: I heard Allah's Messenger- peace be upon him- saying, "The reward of deeds depends upon the intentions and every person will receive the rewards according to what he has intended. So, whoever emigrates for the sake of Allah and His Messenger, his emigration will be (counted as being) for Allah and His Messenger, and whoever emigrates for worldly benefits or for a woman to marry, his emigration will be (counted as being) for what he emigrated for"(Bukhari, 1/6). Also, Abu Hurairah narrated that the Messenger of Allah -peace be upon him- said: "The oath is based upon what will make your companion believe you."”(Moslem, 1653/3).

In an attempt by the researchers to reach a specified timing of intention can be included into the conceptual framework of financial statements, to raise and focus the importance of intention and significant influence of it on recognition, classification, measurement and presentation of the items, has developed a proposed model, followed by an example shows the timing of the intention and its impact on the preparation of financial statements, as in The following two figures:

Figure (B-1): Example of timing of intention

Figure (B-2): example of timing of intention

Applying rules of Islamic religion on intention as a concept in IFRS

Through applying the rules of intention in Islamic religion that will be discussed in details later in preparing financial statements, researchers found that the connection point between intention and event will be prior to the initial recognition, however, the recognition of any item within financial statements may be considered as the resulted event of intention of preparers of financial statements which should appear presumptions and justifications in the accompanying disclosures. The researchers have proposed three bases must be found in all the accounting transactions to be recognized as follow:

a-The intention beyond the transaction

b- Transaction or event

c-Recognition as a result of transaction or event, followed by other accounting procedures like classification and measurement .

The researchers tried to propose through this study criteria to recognize the intention of preparers of financial statements, as in the following figure:

Figure (B-3): criteria of intention

Conceptual framework for intention according to Islamic religion

Nature of humanity has apparent behaviors represented in specific characteristics distinguish between a person from others, but these characteristics emanate from inward source could be called intention, that kept the human being whether good or bad.

Researchers summarized rules of intention in Islamic religion that can be used to propose a module for intention could be included in the conceptual framework of financial statements of financial statements set by IASB through the following figure (4):

Figure (4): rules of intention in Islamic religion

Possibility of proposing a conceptual framework for intention in IFRSs and including it in the disclosures accompanying the financial statements

In this part of the study and according to Conceptual framework for intention according to Islamic religion, the researchers try to connect between accounting concepts and conceptual framework of intention showed in figure (4), in order to reach to relevant conceptualization for intention in IFRS, thus, researchers allocate accounting practices to rules of intention in Islamic religion as is shown in figure (5):

Figure (5): Allocation of accounting practices according to Islamic rules of intention

Intention as content of conceptual framework of financial statement

The researchers propose through this study, a concept of the intention included within the conceptual framework of the financial statements, which describes the main concepts of the preparation and presentation the financial statements, and specifically within the qualitative characteristics of financial information which can be defined as: "attributes characterize the information presented in the financial statements so that be useful and can be used properly as a basis for making decisions about the reporting entity by the users of financial statements".

Qualitative Characteristics divided into two sections:

- 1- Fundamental Characteristics
- 2- Enhancing Characteristics

The researchers tried to include the concept of the intention within the fundamental characteristics which identified with two special characteristics:

- 1- **Relevance:** The presented financial information be relevant to the decision would be taken, in addition to its ability to make a difference in the decisions taken by the users.
- 2- **Faithful Representation:** the financial information be represented faithfully transactions and events that occurred in the entity, which has been expressed in the financial statements.

The researchers propose the inclusion of the concept of the intention within the faithful representation characteristic, to provide information characterized by a high degree of credibility and transparency necessary to grant the related parties trust and confidence when they need these statements during the decision-making process.

And so the researcher's included the intention within a faithful representation characteristic as is shown in the following figure(6):

Definition of intention included in IFRSs

According to all of the foregoing, the researchers are able to develop a definition of intention concept in accounting that can be included in IFRSs within the qualitative characteristics in the conceptual framework of the financial statements, as follows:

Intention: Intended motivation precedes the initial recognition of the items included in the financial statements, it reflects the actual objectives behind the recognition of items in the financial statements corresponded with the classification presented. Whether using accepted accounting practices, or unaccepted accounting practices.

So, intention can be influenced by two standards:

a- **Objective standard:** relates to accepted accounting practices according to IFRS.

b- **Subjective criterion:** Take into account the person who prepared the financial statements or the decision-maker in the preparation of financial statements, in the light of what was issued about the finance and accounting practices and behaviors, whether accepted or unaccepted.

According to for mentioned two standards, there are two related behaviors can be categorized as follow:

a- **Good Intention:** emanates from accepted accounting practices, and aim to present real financial statements are presented according to the accounting practice that fit with the recognition process leading to the reliable and transparent financial statement .

b- **Bad Intention:** emanates from unacceptable accounting practices and aim to present financial statements in contrary to its reality too, leading to the submission of misleading information lacks to faithfully and fair presentation.

The following figure (7) shows the contents of the conceptual framework of intention in accounting to be included in the framework of the financial statements:

Conclusion

Researchers focus in the importance of intention, as the actions of human being have two sides, the shown one that relates to the seen behaviors and practices, the other side relates to the hidden beliefs and unseen objectives that absolutely affect shown side, this called intention.

There is no conceptualization to intention in IFRS in spite of redundancy of intention in most IFRS, the researchers try to set a conceptual framework to intention derived from Islamic religion, and include it in the conceptual framework of financial statements, as the main content of fundamental qualitative characteristic that called representational faithfulness.

Researchers also benefit from the rules of intention in Islamic religion to allocate accounting practices to these rules.

According to the aforementioned researchers can draw the following results:

1. The presence of conceptual framework in the Islamic religion, includes fourteen rules relate to intention and its influence on all behaviors of a human being, some of these practices are accounting practices that included in IFRS.
2. The possibility of setting conceptual framework to intention in IFRS derived from Islamic religion that includes a conceptual framework, this framework consist of definition of intention, its fourteen rules, types of intention: bad and good, and the influence of intention of process of preparation of financial statements that called accounting cycle, basically include recognition, classification, measurement, and disclosures, these concepts can be controlled and driven by intention, so as to use objective quantitative measurement bases consistently, and not to change it except in there are objective sufficient evidences for the convenient of stakeholders about the necessity of the change.
3. The possibility of include intention concept in the conceptual framework of financial statements set by IASB, within fundamental qualitative characteristics , under a new content of representational faithfulness called correspondence between practice and intention.

4. the possibility of determining the places in IFRS that intention plays main rule in its identification through studying and analyzing financial statements carefully, in spite of not disclosing the intention, but evidenced by classification and measurement of items in the financial statements.
5. Intention control accounting practices according to IFRS, many of these practices depend on the undeclared intention of an entity, regardless of its acceptance or not, to achieve hidden interests through financial statements.

Recommendations

1. The integrity of religion and practices in sciences, because of the absolute presence of hidden intentions beyond it. to control over these practices.
2. Proposing a conceptual framework for intention, under fundamental characteristics in the conceptual framework for financial statements, as the content of representational faithfulness, that lead to increasing level of transparency of accounting information that presented to the interests of stakeholders.
3. The necessity of including additional disclosures relate to intention in accounting, so as to differentiate between accepted accounting principles and non accepted, for the purposes of determining good or bad intention behind these practices for management by the stakeholders.
4. The necessity of including disclosures with different matters related to personal judgments of management that actually its real intentions closed to reality that expressed in financial statements, which results in helping users of these statements to treat with failures, and minimizes the cavities in accounting practices according to IFRS.
5. The necessity of documentation of intention in initial recognition for items included in financial statements, with big concern to that by the external auditor, to follow up the accounting practices during the next short-term periods so as to determine any deviations in the entity between actual practices and what should be, to make necessary corrections.
6. The necessity of increasing professional skepticism by the audit entities in its employees that resulted in inconveniences with the presented information included in financial statements and related disclosures, and looking for other deep evidence to assure of intention of the entity.
7. Impose legal constraints limit change in disclosed intentions of management for consistency and comparability the purposes, and also not to make the financial statements misunderstanding and ambiguous.

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